

THE ISSUE OF DECORATIONS IN THE ARCHITECTURE OF MODERN MOSQUES

A.N. Sultanov

Samarkand State Architectural and Civil Engineering University

Head of the "Art" Department

R.S. Muqimov

Tajik technical university named after academician M.S. Osimi

Abstract: This article discusses advanced traditions in forming the architecture and decorations of modern mosques, grandeur in the architecture of the building, compositional unity, the symmetry of the main facade, the leadership of the prayer hall and the dome, decorations in minaret architecture, the spatial characteristics of the prayer hall interior, architectural and artistic emphasis on the mihrab, dome shape and solutions under the dome, the use of geometric patterns, islamic calligraphy, kundal and muqarnas in mosque decorations and ornamentation, the entrance doors to the building, architectural leadership and harmony in building style and artistic completeness.

Certain parts of the mosque structure inherently require decoration. Architects pay special attention to the interior and exterior views of the mosque, including doors, columns, column-beam structures, mihrab and its surroundings, railings, ceilings, minarets, and pedestals. And this article discusses about them.

Keywords: Mosque, architecture, mihrab, decoration, prayer, interior, ornament, composition, guzars, muqarnas, dome, khanaqah, structural, girih, Islamic, decorations, sharafa.

Introduction: Attention to the construction of religious buildings and mosques and their architecture, which fulfill people's freedom of religious belief and worship, has been formed since ancient times and is developing day by day.

Among the existing religions in the world, the youngest and the most comprehensive secular religion is the religion of Islam. The number of people professing this religion and the number of mosques being built are also increasing rapidly. Currently, there are more than 5 million mosques in the world. The development of world architecture, its modern creative trends have an impact on the architecture of mosque buildings. For this reason, changes are being felt in the architecture of the mosques that are currently being built. These changes are mainly related to the "looks" of mosque architecture, exteriors and interiors, and the Islamic worship process and its requirements have been preserved. Among the scientific researches and architectural projects carried out in the countries of the world, including the Islamic countries, the number of works focused on the architecture of mosques is relatively small, but they are aimed at finding modern methods and ideas for the architectural formation of the architecture of mosques. And in Uzbekistan, such actions are now being revived. Most of the mosque buildings that have been designed and built so far are based on the architecture of historical mosques. At the same time, in Uzbekistan, as in foreign Islamic and Eurasian countries, there is a need to make changes to the architecture of mosque buildings and their structure based on modern aesthetic and social requirements.

During the years of independence, freedom of religious belief was established in Uzbekistan, and the construction of mosques is progressing in terms of number and quality. Mosques, which are considered the House of Allah, are considered as public buildings, and attention is paid to their architecture and architectural-artistic solutions. The Fatwa of the Supreme Islamic Office on the issue of the place of women in mosques

was accepted. Currently, there are 2101 registered mosques in our republic, which are renovated or newly built mosques. By 2025, there is a need to build more than 100 mosques in our republic. This need is increasing year by year. At the moment, in our republic, special QMQ construction norms and rules for the design and construction of mosques have not yet been developed. Questions such as the architecture of modern mosque buildings, determining the place of women in them, designing parking lots for worshippers, the content of decorations and the number of minarets in mosques, the typology and function of modern mosques are still left open. The supervision of the ongoing projects and the mosques under construction, and their architectural solutions, are entrusted to the attention of Islamic organizations. As a result, in the architecture of newly built mosque buildings, the advanced traditions of the world experience in this field are being poorly paid attention to. These issues and problems show the relevance and necessity of the topic of this dissertation.

Research problem. In recent years, many modern buildings of mosques have been designed and put into practice in many foreign countries. However, in our republic, the basics of designing modern mosques and the issues of their architectural and urban planning remain open. The typology of modern mosques, in contrast to Guzar, Juma, Jame and namazgahs, which were widespread in the past, is now much reduced: it is formed in the style of neighborhood and jame mosques, and the functions of the former Juma and namazgah mosques are now assigned to jame mosques. grandeur in the architecture of the building, compositional unity, the symmetry of the main facade, the leadership of the prayer hall and the dome, decorations in minaret architecture, the spatial characteristics of the prayer hall interior, architectural and artistic emphasis on the mihrab, dome shape and solutions under the dome, the use of geometric patterns, islamic calligraphy, kundal and muqarnas in mosque decorations and ornamentation, the entrance doors to the building,

architectural leadership and harmony in building style and artistic completeness; additional functions, such as library and hadith study rooms, bookstore, and guardhouses, have been determined in the structure of the mosque building. There are problems in the composition (territory) of the mosque building, in terms of allocating a place for praying women and its architectural organization, as well as organizing a place for the shoes of praying people in mosques. The problems of organizing and determining the number of minarets in the dimensional solution and architecture of mosques have not been studied.

Literature analysis and methods. Mosques have an important position in the religious and social life of the countries of the Muslim East. That is why mosques in the past occupied a leading place in the historical cities of Central Asia from the point of view of religious, political and urban planning.

Hazrat Khizr Mosque was built first in Samarkand. Later, in the 9th-12th centuries, and especially during the Timurid period, the size-planning and compositional solutions of mosques developed. All mosques and their types are the result of several centuries of activity of Muslims to complete prayer. Therefore, mosques are the most important structures in Islam, and their construction is considered important. In this way, during the development of mosques, their following types arose:

1. Namazgoh (or musallo), it is also called iydgoh;
2. Jome mosques;
3. Neighborhood guzars and village mosques;
4. Mosques under other types of buildings and structures;
5. Pilgrimage mosques in mausoleums;
6. House-mosques.

Depending on the types of mosques, their location, capacity, group of rooms and their area, functional-design structure, etc. change. Large mosques are in courtyard composition, with large prayer halls located along intersecting perpendicular axes of symmetry. Typical mosques have a compact layout, with volumes arranged around a main center or axis. These include mosques near mahallas and mausoleums. Mosques with inner courtyards are characterized by mutually perpendicular axes of symmetry and domed halls located on these axes. Columned porches surround the rest of the yard. For example, the Kalon Mosque in Bukhara, the Bibikhanim Mosque in Samarkand, and the Anau Mosque in Turkmenistan have kept the main axes of symmetry even though they have an open courtyard.

Various solutions of Central Asian column-beam devices-orders are used in mosques. Their interiors are decorated with mulberry heads mounted on columns and the ceiling with exquisite and unusual patterns. Ponsod in Bukhara and Shahrisabz, Hazrat Khizr mosques in Samarkand and others are among them.

The characteristics of the architecture of historical mosques are mainly the following: the built mosque buildings are formed on the basis of local building

materials and building construction traditions, and the architectural-planning solutions of most mosques, especially the mosques, are mainly of two types: 1) compact (compact) composition with a porch with an inner hall; 2) the use of compositions with a symmetrical inner courtyard relative to the longitudinal axis. In the first type of mosques, the porches are facing the outside of the building, on one, two or three sides, and in the second type of mosques, the rooms and porches are facing the inner courtyard.

The exterior and interior of the mosque are made in harmony with unique girih, Islamic-scriptural decorations, honors, muqarnas and other ornaments and colors. These features have been developed and modernized over the centuries. Most of them are characteristic of modern mosques.

Development ways and types of mosque decoration are reflected in the specific features of the exterior and interior decoration of the architecture of mosques. In the construction of the first mosques in Central Asia, no attention was paid to decoration. The issue of decorating the mosque arose from the architectural composition of the interior, the function of its parts, and the skillful use of building materials. That's why the decoration is given only to the mihrab, the corners under the dome, and to the columns in interiors with wooden ceilings.

Decoration of ceilings with elegant colorful patterns has been widely used since the 15th century. In the 16th century, in the interior of mosques, the shield-like surfaces under the dome, the borders of the arches were marked with blue color. This event was also caused by the effect of the under-dome structural base, that is, it is aimed at artisticizing the interior construction. The colorful decorations used on the ceiling and domes helped to balance the beauty of the mosque. In the hot and dry climate of Central Asia, elegant blue colors give a feeling of coolness to those sitting in the building. It is also connected with the flowery carpets laid on the floor of the mosque, creating a comfortable atmosphere that does not distract the imagination of the worshiper.

From the 9th to the 10th centuries, the interior and exterior of mosques were decorated with Arabic calligraphy inscriptions reflecting morals, education and Islamic concepts. Over time, Arabic letters even became a symbol of Islam. Epigraphic patterns were so developed in the Islamic world that they even rose to the level of great art in architecture.

In the 10th-12th centuries, clay gypsum and brick carving were widely used in interior decoration. In the interior, the shelves were marked with two colored decorative columns. The patterns on the wall of the qibla side of the mosque were not distracting one's imagination.

Since the 14th century, the interiors have been decorated with a monumental pattern. Plant-like and geometric patterns were made on the surface of the wall with glue colors. Most of the decorative composition was occupied by gilded motifs. As an example, the dome of the 16th century Khoja Zainiddin mosque in Bukhara was covered with a small gilded plant-like

pattern. The lower part of the dome was decorated with bagals, mihrab and two arched parts with complex decorations. The ceiling of the "Baland" mosque in Bukhara was made of wood, the surface of which consisted of a polygonal central orange and multiple star-like patterns arranged around it. The walls of the mosque were painted with white and were divided into different sections by means of embossed clay gypsum lines.

Since the 16th century, the interior of the mosque and the porch walls have been attracting attention with their richly decorated ceilings and colorful patterns. In the 16th and 20th centuries, neighborhood mosques were necessarily rooms, and adjacent to their outer walls, summer prayer places - porches, a pool, minaret or mezona, and several rooms and additional rooms were built. The columns in the porch of such mosques, the entrance doors to the mosque were decorated with wooden carvings, clay gypsum carvings on the inner and outer walls, sometimes tile patterns, and ceilings were decorated with paint patterns.

But the architects also contributed by building and decorating mosques to inculcate Islam in their hearts and call them to worship. For this, the architects paid special attention to the interior and exterior of the mosque and the mihrabs. The doors, columns, columns and beams of mosques, mihrab and its surroundings, fences, ceilings, minarets, columns - all these were the focus of the architects. For example, the mihrab was supposed to attract people with its beautiful, "immaculate decoration", instilled confidence and inclination towards Islam in the person's heart, inviting them to attend the mosque.

Due to the lack of stable traditions of the 17th century, its contribution to the development of architectural ceramics is not felt. Since the masters of this period did not depend on a strictly defined style, they often referred to previous experiences. For example, in the Chor-Bakr complex near Bukhara, double bricks were made with patterns similar to the "bandak" type. Gavkushan Tower, built in Bukhara in the XVI-XVII centuries, was tried to resemble Minorai Kalon.

In the "Tomb of Khoja" mausoleum, built in Namangan in the second half of the 18th century, an attempt was made to restore the terracotta cut of the 12th century and the ceramic style of the 14th century. However, although the cutting of the clay was relatively successful, it used dark green, reddish-orange and blue glazes that spoiled the general harmony of the coating.

The stylistic integrity of colors can be observed in the terracotta and clay ceramic-based rivet coverings presented only for XIX century Khiva structures. In most cases, the rivets were covered with white glaze patterns, and the pattern lines were drawn in black paint. Individual elements of the pattern were covered with blue and sometimes green tiles. Patterned or epigraphic subjects were often carved on large square or rectangular surfaces from riveted boards. They were

numbered so as not to get confused when gluing the boards to the wall.

Numbers or symbols were placed on the back of the product. In the 19th century, the numbers of the boards made in Khiva were written on the surface of the rivet in an unknown way, and they became part of the pattern. 19th-century Khiva enamel paints are characterized by low gloss, dryness, non-transparent paint, pattern of rivets, and the fact that the paint sometimes bleeds or mixes during the cooking of the glaze.

In its place, it is appropriate to say that similarities with the cut ceramic mosaic of the 17th century are not found in the decoration of the buildings of the 19th century.

In the mosques of Central Asia, patterns are found in the interiors of buildings, on the interior walls, columns, ceilings and dome decorations. In the wall patterns, mainly triangular, rhombic and writing patterns were used in combination with Islamic decorations. For example, in ancient times, a downward-pointing triangle represented a male symbol, while an upward-pointing triangle represented a female symbol. From their joining, a rhombus shape was created, which symbolized new life.

For this reason, in Islamic aesthetics, the shape and decoration of architectural buildings symbolically represent the spiritual world, lifestyle, meaning of life, purpose and content of living.

Since ancient times, natural light and color palette have been considered a source of emotional and aesthetic excitement in man. We can see the color culture reflected in Central Asian architecture and ornamentation, particularly in temple structures.

In many cultures, light is a symbol of divine unity. In Islamic architecture, light serves as decoration by changing other elements or forming patterns. In the right lighting, the patterns of light passing through appear like a muted, latticed, gridded, disembodied screen. Light can give architecture a dynamic quality by expanding patterns, shapes and structures across time scales. The combination of light and shadow creates strong contrasts of planes and creates a texture (structure) and a unique plasticity on embossed stone and tile or brick surfaces.

Secondly, it was impossible to ignore the decoration of the mosque. It was necessary to involve the common people to worship together in the mosques. The mosque was considered a place of obedience and prayer, the most pure and attentive place. It should attract a person's attention with its beauty and coziness, and educate their aesthetic outlook.

The mosque is economical and rational with its beauty and decoration, and at the same time, it leaves an unnatural impression on a person. That is why religious monuments, including mosques, were not devoid of decoration.

In Central Asia, the decoration of the interior of mosques was used in the rhythm. The style of decorating a mirror top with a pattern, which was used in palaces and residences in Central Asia, particularly in Bukhara,

was almost never used, not only on the western wall of the mosques, but also on the mosque itself.

It should be said that some parts of the mosque building require decoration in terms of their structure. In particular, the corners of a domed building cannot be left open when changing from a rectangle to an octagon. In the interior, those places of the mosque need to be filled with something. It was in this place that the architects found it necessary to use the polygonal design called sharafa. It was to this place that Sharafa came into use. Since Sharafa is composed of unique forms, muqarnas, despite being a constructive element, it also performed the function of a majestic decoration. If only a little color is given to the sharafa, it will give a special artistic beauty to the interior of the mosque. The fact that the sharafa of the dome served as a constructive basis in the transition from a rectangle to an octagon is evident in the interior of the Yartigumbaz mausoleum in Sarakhs, dating back to the 11th century. This sharafa is made up of large dome and Mekhrab quarters.

Flowers in the pattern: gulsafsar - peace, immortality; wavy stem of a flower - wealth and prosperity; branches and leaves - symbols of youth, concealment; white color - happiness and luck; blue color - high faith; red color is a symbol of joy and youth. The pattern is a necklace that symbolizes peace, mental peace, long life, and infinity. Patterns of architectural buildings are symbols of supreme perfection, perfection, and the way to God. In this way, the symbol of the pattern is the factor of going to the presence of the only and merciful God, who created all beauties and gave them as a blessing to His servants, and attaining His beauty.

Along with flowers and plant-like patterns, fruits are also reflected in folk art and architecture. For example, on the walls of one of the rooms of the Munchogtepa area dating back to the VI-VII centuries, there is an image of a human head and a bunch of grapes. Pomegranate is depicted on the walls of the workshop dating from the 1st-5th centuries, and Anahita, the god of fertility holding a pomegranate, is represented on the figurines from the 1st-3rd centuries and on the pottery of the Middle Ages. In folk home architecture there is also pattern of pomegranate and flower of pomegranate. It should be mentioned that apple is a symbol of love, pomegranate and grapes are considered to be the symbol of goodness and wealth.

The pattern in the form of a cross (idol) has existed in Central Asia since ancient times. Such a pattern was recognized by peoples in different periods as the concept of the emergence of nature, a symbol of the sun, a symbol of death and life. The Ram's horn-like pattern is often used in mountain folk art, wall-painting and pillar capitals. Therefore, the resemblance of the head of the pillar in the houses to the horn of a wild goat or ram is based on the ancient belief that it is a symbol of courage, bravery, and purity, and it is expressed in folk art decoration and wood carving art.

Colors also had their own symbolic meaning. In particular, the blue color was a symbol of the blue sky,

and the blue domes were likened to the sky. At the same time, in some places, blue color was also used as a sign to protect the house from the evil eye.

The embodied analysis of the symbolic expressions of architectural decorations in the parts of architectural monuments (dome, tower, gate, door, sign, pillar, door ring, fence, mukarnas, mikhrab and so on) indicates that they have an interconnected logical system.

"Kufy" and "Suls" inscriptions in the patterns of the mosque express the longing feelings of a Muslim's lonely communication with Allah. The intricate, Islamic writing patterns in the mosque are a symbol that vividly expresses the essence of Islam, the way of life and aesthetic views of a Muslim, which instills the beauty of God into the human heart," writes Professor E. Umarov [10]. There is also a symbol of supreme perfection, the way to God in the patterns of the mosque building.

"According to Islamic concepts, the beauty of buildings is not in the appearance and number of statues of idols and figures, living beings, but in the mutual geometrical harmony of the architectural forms of the buildings, the harmony of colors and shapes, open and closed courtyards and rooms, porches with each other, in its comfortable and organic connection, in the proportion of geometrical and Islamic complex patterns, and finally, in the neat architectural environment decorated with written patterns and the beautiful hearts and virtuous people in them, the great wisdoms taken from the Holy Kur'an and hadiths, which call people to beautiful behavior" [9].

Over the next ten years, in the experience of mosque construction, colorful (floral), decorative, modern decoration materials, absorbing a number of national traditions, 1) koshin-parchin patterns (around altar); 2) Wall patterns; 3) Geometric patterns cut from MDF sheets using a router the trend of using patterned grids (in the altar and on the pulpit) was born.

In the Tillakori Madrasah in Samarkand, the style of riveted coverings was used, but the quality was much lower: the paint was dull or, on the contrary, sharply rendered. On the rivets, the gold cases corresponding to the name of the madrasa were made of gold that did not correspond to the real gold of the XIV-XVI centuries.

The small-sized tiles in the Nadir Devonbegi Madrasah in Samarkand are made on the basis of light-white, high-quality faience.

In some places, it is possible to observe that ceramics have been replaced by its mirror image. For example, in the entrance style and minaret of the Hazrat Khizr Mosque in Samarkand, there are cases of work similar to the tiling coating with various paints with clay plaster. This style is called "Kirma" style.

Instead of the conclusion, we will briefly explain what was brought to the development of architectural ceramic coverings, i.e. decorative decorations, in each separate period.

The period up to the 10th century AD can be considered as the period when ceramics sought innovation, replacing the raw clay pieces that preceded

it, sometimes together with them, and in some cases, adding to the decoration of buildings.

Starting from the 10th century, ceramic coverings occupy an absolutely clear place in architectural decoration as the main copy, first in the form of facing brick and parts made from it. Later, they became more complex and were used together with cross-cut ganch, and in the 12th century they played a major role in the cladding of buildings. The masters have reached perfection in the processing of ceramics, which they use in the decoration of buildings, in order to express their artistic ideas and reach a much higher level.

In the 13th century, mysterious paints were added to architectural ceramics in a still unreliable and very rare way to show the elegance and richness of the incised ceramic design.

The 14th century was the flourishing period of architectural ceramics, that is, it is distinguished by the mass use of mysterious paints. It is also characterized by a kind of standardization of ceramic pieces that began in the pre-Mongol period, i.e., a complete end to the designation of unconditional generalized copies for ceramic pieces. The variety, richness and care of the ceramic types indicate the high level of skill of the tilers of that time and their developed artistic perception and taste in creating new types of ceramic coverings.

In the 15th century, the large-scale growth of construction and the majesty of buildings increased the demand for ceramic coverings, which were fashionable during this period. Their mass production and use goes hand in hand with the high level of craftsmanship in the processing of these products and the uniqueness of the architectural style. These periods is characterized by an increase in luxury, a variety of decorations, and by the end of the century, more delicacy and beauty appear in the general structure and parts of the coverings.

The 16th century can be considered the age of architectural faience. Craftsmen use faience, that is, clay with added ganch, more effectively than clay pottery. Although not completely different from earlier period coatings, the coatings of this period are characterized by their own durable decorative styles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The analysis of decorations in the interiors of most modern (newly built) mosques allowed us to determine the importance of the following traditional artistic solutions in them:

- the use of geometric (girih) and plant-like (Islamic) patterns made in different ways, bars for covering windows;
- use of khoshiya, sharafa, ravok, kundal and traditional muqarnas patterns in the decoration of dome devices and mihrabs;
- the use of inscriptional decorations (in the decoration of the walls, around the altar and the flanges of the dome).

In the mosques of Central Asia, patterns are found in the mihrab decorations of buildings, interior walls, columns, ceilings, and dome decorations. In the mural patterns, mainly triangular, rhombic and script patterns were used in combination with Islamic decorations. A

7-pointed star pattern is used on the walls and domes of some mosques.

Over the next ten years, in the experience of mosque construction, colorful (floral), decorative, modern decoration materials, absorbing a number of national traditions, 1) Tile-rivet patterns (around altar), 2) Wall patterns, 3) Geometric patterns cut from MDF sheets using a rover the trend of using patterned grids (in the altar and minbar) was born.

The architecture of modern mosques built in the years of independence in Uzbekistan will have a unique appearance if they use the traditional forms of decoration typical of the architecture of Islamic culture, such as the khanakah, the dome, mihrab and porches.

Also, elements of folk art, such as historically symbolic dome shapes, decorative artistic decorations, patterns and ornaments, are combined with the necessary decorations in the architecture of newly built mosques.

Conclusion. The building of modern mosques, especially mosques, should be designed in the style of national architectural works of art, they should always have a place in the heart of our people and nation, should be understandable and agreeable to them, should be formed on the basis of universal values, should be very convenient for use and economical in construction. Two of the architectural attributes of the mosque: the minaret and the dome should be visible from the outside.

The mosque should be not just a place of worship, but it also should become an object of pilgrimage that attracts tourists as a priceless architectural object that reflects the architectural decorations, traditions and achievements of the country.

It is impossible to tell or evaluate the harmony of external and internal decorations in mosques, that there are certain laws in their creation, just by mental-visual analysis. This harmony can be fully perceived and evaluated through geometrical and mathematical approaches. In the article, the proportions of the architectural forms, the harmony of the types, shapes and colors of the decorations are taken as a criterion for assessing harmony.

In the interior decorations of mosques, the inscriptions written in Arabic script are not just designs to be seen and enjoyed, but they are decorations that spread Islamic manners and knowledge, God's words and feelings to the people. The building of the mosque and its architecture should be such that whoever enters it, whether he is religious or not, the architectural environment there should arouse in him the desire to pray.

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